

MAIN DIRECTIONS OF STATE SUPPORT FOR INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF SERVICE ENTERPRISES

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Annotation. The article is aimed at analyzing modern directions, mechanisms, and efficiency factors of state support for the activities of service sector enterprises. The study examines the role of public–private sector cooperation in the service industry, the types of financial and non-financial support provided by the state, as well as their impact on the competitiveness of enterprises. In the context of contemporary economic conditions characterized by the growing importance of the service sector, the legal, economic, innovative, and infrastructural factors of state support are systematically analyzed.

Keywords. Service sector, state support, service enterprises, financial support, innovative activity, competitiveness, economic policy.

The service sector is the most dynamically developing sector of the modern market economy, and its share in the national gross domestic product (GDP) is increasing. Service enterprises have become a driving force of economic growth, playing an important role in creating new jobs, meeting the population's need for quality services, and improving regional infrastructure. At the same time, enterprises in this sector, especially small and medium-sized businesses, are faced with limited financial resources, high tax burden, staff shortages, and infrastructure problems. Therefore, the development and implementation of effective mechanisms for state support of service enterprises is becoming an urgent task.

The main goal of state support is to increase competitiveness, stimulate innovative activity, ensure the quality and safety of services, and reduce economic inequality. The main regulatory legal acts on state support for enterprises operating in the service sector in the Republic of Uzbekistan, their date of adoption and by whom they were adopted are listed. (Table 1)

Table 1

№	Name of regulatory legal document	Document number	Date received	Receiving authority
1	On additional measures for the development of the services sector	PD-104	January 27, 2022	President of the Republic of Uzbekistan
2	On measures for the development of the services sector in 2021–2023	PD -5113	May 11, 2021	President of the Republic of Uzbekistan
3	On measures to simplify the provision of public services	PD -113	April 20, 2022	President of the Republic of Uzbekistan
4	On guarantees of freedom of entrepreneurial activity (Law)	LRU-328	May 25, 2012	Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan
5	On public-private partnership (Law)	LRU -537	May 10, 2019	Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan

These regulatory legal acts serve to develop the service sector, support business entities, create new jobs, and ensure healthy competition in the services market. Legal and organizational foundations of state support. The first direction of support for service enterprises is to improve their legal and organizational operating conditions. The state will take the following measures:

- **Simplify licensing procedures:** Provide public services on the basis of the “One Door” principle, cancel unnecessary permits and documents, and create transparent and favorable conditions for starting a business.
- **Provide legal guarantees:** Protect the property rights of service enterprises, strengthen contractual rights, and introduce mechanisms to protect the interests of business entities before state agencies.
- **Develop public-private partnership:** Develop service infrastructure through concessions, state orders, and attracting foreign investment.

Financial support is the most important part of state assistance and is implemented in several areas:

- **Provision of credit resources:** Provision of preferential loans for service enterprises, subsidizing loan interest rates and facilitating access to bank loans through guarantee funds. This is especially important for replenishing working capital, purchasing new equipment and technological modernization.
- **Subsidies and grants:** Provision of targeted subsidies for the development of particularly important types of services (medicine, education, technical assistance). Awarding grants for start-up projects and innovative services on a winning basis.

- Tax incentives: Provision of benefits for profit tax and other taxes for newly opened enterprises, especially for facilities in the regions. Creation of opportunities for deferring or paying value added tax (VAT) payments.
- Insurance mechanisms: Support for entrepreneurial activity through commercial and credit risk insurance, export operations insurance.

The efficiency of service enterprises is directly dependent on the development of infrastructure:

- ✓ Transport and communication infrastructure: Improving the road network, increasing the level of supply of enterprises with electricity, gas and water.
- ✓ Technological infrastructure: Building high-tech service centers, logistics complexes and innovation parks.
- ✓ Improving sanitary and hygienic conditions: Introducing modern standards for food and health service enterprises.

The competitiveness of modern service enterprises depends on innovation and digital transformation:

- Introduction of digital technologies: Financial support for equipping enterprises with automation systems, e-commerce platforms and data processing programs.
- Application of IT technologies: Financing the development of new types of services based on artificial intelligence, blockchain and cloud technologies.
- Development of the start-up ecosystem: Supporting innovative ideas through technopark and incubation centers, financing accelerator programs.

The main factor affecting the quality of the service sector is the qualification of personnel:

- ❖ Vocational education: Implementation of cooperation agreements between vocational education institutions and service enterprises, introduction of a dual education system.

- ❖ **Advanced training:** Regular retraining of employees based on foreign and national experience, introduction of a certification system.
- ❖ **Labor market policy:** Creation of social guarantees and incentive mechanisms for service sector specialists.

The development of service exports contributes to the diversification of the national economy:

- **International certificates:** Reimbursement of certification costs according to ISO and other international standards.
- **Marketing and promotion:** Financing participation in international fairs, exhibitions and conferences, promotion of national service brands in foreign markets.
- **Foreign exchange:** Attracting foreign experts within the framework of state programs and sending local specialists to study in leading countries.

Sustainable development of the service network in the regions:

Regional programs: Providing additional subsidies and benefits for the provision of medical, educational and other public services in rural areas.

Cluster approach: Developing regional service clusters, improving the service delivery network from large centers to small cities and villages.

Direct support to the population Subsidizing services provided to low-income and socially vulnerable populations.

State support for the activities of service enterprises in the service sector requires a comprehensive system and includes several main areas. According to the results of the study, the most effective areas of state support are financial mechanisms (soft loans and tax breaks), stimulating innovative activities, and improving the personnel training system.

The following proposals have been developed to increase the effectiveness of state support:

1. Introduction of a comprehensive approach: Each support area should be implemented in an interconnected manner, and financial, legal and infrastructural measures should be used together.
2. Improvement of the monitoring and evaluation system: Development of a system of indicators to measure the effectiveness of state support programs, analysis of results and adjustment of programs as necessary.
3. Taking into account regional characteristics: Pay special attention to the service sector in Regional Development Programs to reduce economic inequality in the regions.
4. Introduction of digital platforms: Development of electronic platforms and artificial intelligence-based recommendation systems to ensure transparency in the distribution of state support and create convenience for enterprises.
5. Strengthening cooperation with the private sector: Joint development of infrastructure facilities and improvement of service quality through expansion of public-private partnership mechanisms.
6. Export-oriented support: Development of separate programs for the development of service exports and promotion of adaptation to international standards.

In conclusion, thanks to effective state support, service enterprises will increase their competitiveness, develop innovative services and will be able to fully satisfy the population's need for high-quality services. This, in turn, will ensure sustainable growth of the national economy and an increase in the standard of living of the population.

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